

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NANO-PHASED THERMOPLASTIC STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: In this study polypropylene was infused with low weight percentages of Cloisite®15A nanoclays i.e. 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 5 wt. %. A melt blending technique was used to infuse the clays into the polypropylene. Both virgin and infused polypropylene structures were then subjected to quasi-static mechanical tests. Test results revealed that the failure strength, failure strain, stiffness and fracture properties of the nano-structure were enhanced when compared to the unmodified structure. In general the mechanical properties improved with an increase in nanoclay loading up to a threshold of 2 wt. %, thereafter the material properties degraded. At lower clay concentrations, effective dispersion of the nanoclay particles results in the formation of exfoliated and intercalated nanoscale structures as well as high density grain boundaries. Low magnification SEM images for 0.5-2 wt. % specimens indicate that high-density grain boundaries exist on the fractured surfaces of tensile tested specimens. Analysis of failure modes with clay loadings greater than 2 wt % indicates an embrittlement in the polymer structure due to the formation of agglomerated clay sites in the structure. These phase separated composite structures create high stress zones at which the failures occurred.

KEYWORDS: Polypropylene nanocomposites, montmorillonite (MMT), melt intercalation, exfoliation, intercalation, embrittlement, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

1. INTRODUCTION

Since its inception as a new materials technology in 1993, polymer / clay nanocomposites have rapidly grown in reputation. Intense investigative research, first reported by the Toyota research group, has shown that polymer nanocomposites are a cost effective alternative as compared to conventionally filled polymers [1, 2, 3].

Recently, conventionally filled polymers, used widely in the production of components for high end usage, have proven to be extremely costly. The availability and amount of the filler material used in the production of these components are factors responsible for this. With talc or mica (conventional fillers), between 15 wt. % to 50 wt. % filler content can be used to produce an automotive component depending on the type or function of that component. On the other hand, if nanoclays (MMT) are used, approximately 5 wt. % can be used to deliver better mechanical performance compared to components using higher weight loadings of conventional filler materials. The significant reduction in weight results in a lower manufacturing costs and lighter weight components. From a design perspective the reduced weight of the components makes for more fuel efficient products.

The improvements in mechanical and physical properties that nanocomposites have to offer have widened the use of polymers in industry. The improved mechanical and thermal

properties might even extend the use of polymers for under-the-hood applications in the automotive industry. The excellent barrier properties combined with good transparency make them ideal for packaging applications

Polymer nanocomposites can be described as structures that are formed by infusing layered-silicate clay into a thermosetting or thermoplastic polymer matrix. Effective dispersion of the nanoclays within the polymer matrix results in enhancing the mechanical properties.

Morphological analyses of these structures reveal that they can be categorized into three general types, a conventional composite where the nanoclay acts as conventional filler, intercalated nanocomposite which consists of a regular insertion of polymer between the silicate layers and exfoliated nanocomposite where 1 nm thick silicate layers are dispersed within the polymer matrix [4, 5]. These types of nanocomposites are shown in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Schematic of different composites arising from the interaction of layered silicates and polymers [5].

R. K. Bharadwaj *et al.* suggests that the mechanical properties of a virgin polymer are enhanced when exfoliation occurs with extremely low concentrations of nanoclays (1 wt. % to 3 wt. %) as compared to conventional phase-separated composites of a filler material in a polymer. The large surface area available for interactions with the polymer matrix coupled with high aspect ratio is responsible for the enhancement in properties [6].

In this study organically modified montmorillonite clay (MMT) is used as the reinforcement particles. MMT or layered aluminosilicates are crystalline materials consisting of approximately 1 nm thick layers (sheets) ranging between 30-2000 nm in diameter (figure 2). Infusion of these particles into a polymer matrix often displays superior properties in comparison with micro and macro constituents. Many researchers have described increases in strength, stiffness, thermal/oxidative stability and barrier properties as well as unique properties like self-extinguishing behaviour and tuneable biodegradability during the past decade [7]. These property enhancements and revelation of new properties can only be accessible when the nanoscale morphology and basic physics associated with the property coincide [6, 7].

Fig. 2: Structure of 2:1 phyllosilicates (MMT, Hectorite, Saponite) [5].

The Toyota research group reported that polymer nanocomposite materials exhibited enhanced mechanical, thermal, flammability and barrier properties with less than 5 wt. % nanoclay loading [1, 2, 3]. Their pioneering research involving nylon 6 (polyamide-PA) and montmorillonite (MMT) nanocomposite hybrid structures served as the foundation for research to be conducted on other polar polymers. In most cases, successful results were reported about nanocomposites synthesised using a polar polymer. However, for polymers with low polarity, such as polyolefins, e.g. polypropylene (PP) or poly vinyl chloride (PVC), the current results are not satisfactory. This can be owed to the low compatibility between the nanoclay (MMT) and polyolefins polymer matrix [8].

Polyolefins, especially PP is one of the most widely used thermoplastics in most industrial applications. Availability and low cost is the direct result of large volumes of this material being consumed at industrial level. Polypropylene however has its shortcomings. Low strength and stiffness, low service temperature and weak barrier properties does not make polypropylene the most ideal thermoplastic to use. To overcome these problems traditional filler materials such as talc and mica have been infused into the PP structure. Although the fillers increased strength and stiffness, they rendered the composite material with low impact strength and recyclability. The use of layered silicate materials alleviated these property trade-offs to some extent but the low compatibility between MMT nanoclays and PP resulted in degradation of mechanical performance at higher clay loadings.

Recent advances in polymer clay nanocomposites have yielded two major methods to increase the compatibility between the MMT nanoclays and PP matrix. These are in situ polymerisation and melt intercalation [9]. In the in situ polymerisation method, the clay is used as a catalyst carrier. The propylene monomer intercalates into the interlayer space of the clay and then polymerizes there. The macromolecule chains exfoliate the silicate layers evenly dispersing them in the polymer matrix.

In the melt intercalation method, PP and nanoclays are compounded in the melt to form nanocomposites. As the hydrophilic clay is incompatible with polypropylene, compatibilisation between the clay and PP is necessary to form stable PP nanocomposites. This can be achieved via two synthetic routes. In the first route, the clay can be organically modified by the use of a semi-fluorinated surfactant. If the semi-fluorinated surfactant is used appropriately the resulting organoclay will promote PP/clay miscibility effectively [10]. The second route is to use a compatibiliser, such as maleic anhydride grafted PP (PP-MAH) [11, 2]. The clay is melt compounded with the more polar compatibiliser to form an intercalated master batch. The master batch is then compounded with the neat PP to form the PP

nanocomposite. In this way, the PP-MAH pretreated OMMT is dispersed uniformly in the PP matrix.

In this study we wish to manufacture nano infused thermoplastic structures using melt blending (melt intercalation) with a view of enhancing its mechanical properties and to fully characterise such structures using SEM.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and Preparation of Nanocomposite Specimens

Nanophased thermoplastic composite structures were prepared by infusion of Cloisite®15A nanoclays (Southern Clay Products, USA) into a polypropylene matrix (COSMOPLENE®Y101E, CHEMPRO, SA) using the melt blend technique. Polypropylene (PP) pellets were heated to its melt temperature (Table 1) in a LABCON HTR2 environmental chamber. To avoid thermal shock, the temperature was ramped up by 10°C/min to a maximum temperature of 170°C. Upon reaching the desired temperature, the material was left in the oven at the set temperature to effect temperature soaking. The temperature was measured using a (TESTO QTA25-T4 PYROMETER) probe with the LACON HTR2 digital display. The plastic surface and chamber temperature was measured accurately within a ± 2°C range thus allowing successful control of temperature ramping. A very viscous homogenous molten plastic at melt temperature was then removed and cooled at room temperature (25°C) to form a virgin panel. A similar technique was employed to manufacture the nanophased structures except the temperature was ramped at 10°C/min to a significantly higher temperature than the corresponding melt temperature. The higher temperature setting was used to produce a less viscous polymer matrix to enable better nanoclay dispersion via blending. The increase in temperature rendered the molten plastic to be less viscous thus enabling an easier mixing process. At this stage Cloisite®15A nanoclays measured in specific weight percentages 0.5; 1; 2; 3; 5 were added to separate batches of the molten plastic. The mixtures were vigorously blended using a paddle stirrer for approximately 3 minutes, then cast in moulds and allowed to cure at room temperature. Test coupons were cut from these panels.

In this study polypropylene infused with a specific weight percentage of Cloisite®15A nanoclays is represented by the abbreviation, PP, followed by nominal weight percentage of nanoclay additive. i.e. PP01%CL15A represents polypropylene infused with 1% by weight of nanoclay. All polypropylene nanocomposite specimens will hence forth be referred to using this form.

Table 1: Properties of COSMOPLENE®Y101E

ITEM	UNIT	Y101E	ASTM METHOD
Melt Flow Rate	g/10 mins	17	D1238
Density	g/cm ³	0.90	D1505
Tensile Strength at break	kg/cm ³	350	D638
Elongation	%	>600	D638
Flexural Modulus	kg/cm ²	14,000	D790
Izod Impact strength	kg-cm/cm	2.0	D256
Melting Point	°C	165	N/A

Quasi Static Mechanical Tests

Tensile and flexural tests on the nanocomposite specimens were performed using a Lloyds Tensile Tester fitted with a 20 kN load cell. The tensile and flexural tests were performed using a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min in accordance with the ASTM D3039 standard [15] and ASTM D790 testing standard [16] respectively. Flexural tests were performed on specimens with dimensions 125×13×6 mm using a three-point bend fixture with a span length of 100mm.

The Vickers hardness of the virgin and nano-infused polypropylene specimens was determined using a Matsuzawa DMH2 micro-hardness tester. Specimens of dimension 14 × 12 × 6 mm were indented with a 100 gf load for a period of 5 seconds. The diagonals of the indentation were measured and the Vickers hardness was automatically computed and read of a digital display.

Impact tests were performed on the specimens with dimensions, 40 × 13 × 6 mm using a bench scale Izod impact tester. These specimens were tested according to ASTM D256 testing standard [17].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tensile Tests

The tensile test data obtained was used to plot stress-strain curves for the various nanocomposite structures. Figure 3 shows the average stress-strain data computed for virgin polypropylene specimens.

Fig. 3: Stress versus strain for virgin polypropylene specimens loaded in tension at room temperature (25°C).

The stress-strain response of neat polypropylene shown in figure 1 is typically of visco-elastic thermoplastic materials. Two distinct regions can be seen. The material response initially is fairly linearly followed by a non-linear behaviour. In region 1 (figure 3), up to approximately 10 MPa the material displays an elastic behaviour. Thereafter the graph assumes a non-linear path noticeable in region 2 and is indicative of a ductile response. Typically elastic-plastic failure occurs upon reaching a stress of approximately 25 MPa. The specimens failed with a gentle and low audible snap within the gauge length. The fracture was very clean with minimal fragmentation.

Figure 4 represents a comparative stress versus strain plot for virgin polypropylene specimens versus the nano-infused specimens subjected to tension tests.

Fig. 4: Stress versus strain for PP-Cloisite®15A nanocomposite specimens loaded in tension.

Analysis of the slope of virgin polypropylene in the elastic region of the plot shows an increase in gradient with increasing clay content. The increase in gradient suggests an increase in the material stiffness with an increase in nanoclay loading up to 2 wt. %. Nanocomposite structures containing 3 wt. % and 5 wt. % clay concentrations showed slopes of lower gradient than 0.5 wt. % specimens but were still stiffer than virgin specimens. This is suggestive of stiffness increasing with increasing clay concentration up to 2 wt. % and then decreases for clay concentrations greater than 2 wt. %.

Figure 5 shows the elastic modulus and tensile strength as a function of clay concentration.

Fig. 5: Tensile Strength versus Modulus for PP-Cloisite®15A nanocomposite specimens as a function of clay concentration (wt. %).

Both the tensile strength and the modulus increase in tandem up to 2 wt. % clay concentrations, thereafter-significant degradation occurs. The average modulus and tensile strength for 2 wt. % structures is approximately 120 % and 130 % respectively greater than neat polypropylene. These values peak at 2.3 GPa for modulus and 68 MPa for tensile strength as per table 2.

Table 2: Tensile Properties of Polypropylene Cloisite®15A Nanocomposites

	Clay Content	Modulus	Tensile strength
Specimen	wt %	GPa	MPa
PP-neat	0	1.0	26
PP 005CL15A	0.5	1.6	47
PP01CL15A	1	1.9	60
PP02CL15A	2	2.3	68
PP03CL15A	3	1.5	34
PP05CL15A	5	1.4	24

A sharp decrease subsequently occurs, with 3 wt. % and 5 wt. % specimens dropping to 1.5 GPa and 1.35 GPa respectively. These observations are suggestive of embrittlement occurring in the nanocomposite structures for clay concentrations greater than 2 wt. %. A similar trend for the ultimate tensile strength is shown in figure 5. These findings are consistent to those reported by the Toyota group whose research on polyamide nanocomposites showed stiffness and strength increased by 100 % and 50 % respectively with low nanoclay loadings (less than 4 wt. %), [1, 2, 3]. Similarly, Ding Chao *et al* also reported that the significantly increased mechanical properties at low concentration of nanoclays may be due to the uniformly dispersed MMT tactoid and intercalated structures [8]. The organically modified MMT (OMMT) is intercalated by the PP chains and confines the segmental movement of the PP macro-molecules. As a result, the modulus of the PP nanocomposites increases with OMMT loadings. He also stated that the fraction of intercalated structure decreased with increasing nanoclay content. At higher clay concentrations, aggregation of the nanoclays may occur decreasing the tensile strength and modulus.

Failure of 0.5, 1, and 2 wt. % nanocomposites specimens were very similar to virgin polypropylene specimen. PP03%CL15A and PP05%CL15A specimens shattered with loud snapping noises at failure. The findings here are consistent with the findings reported by R. K. Bharadwaj *et al* [6]. He showed that the elastic modulus for polyester nanocomposites significantly decreased for clay concentrations greater than 2 wt. %. The degradation may be linked to crosslinked bonds decreasing with increasing clay content causing the nanocomposite structures to become more brittle. Examination of the hardness and impact properties, described later, gives more insight about the behaviour of these nanocomposite structures at higher clay concentration.

Flexural Tests

A minimum of three specimens per category were tested in a three point bend configuration. Figure 6 represents the load-deflection data for specimens tested in flexure.

Fig. 6: Flexural load versus deflection for nanocomposite specimens.

The flexural properties of the nanophased structures are significantly higher than its virgin counterpart. At 0.5 wt % clay loading the improvement is of the order of 60 %. Further loading does not affect the properties significantly. Samples with 1, 2, 3, and 5 wt. % clay loading indicate a similar stiffness. The stiffness (table 4) gradually increases from 1 wt. % to 3 wt. % with a decrease in stiffness occurring with the 5 wt. % specimens. Flexural strength for nanocomposite specimens correspondingly increased with increasing clay content. PP03CL15A specimens display the highest strength values (94.45 MPa), an increase of 85 %. These findings are indicative that degradation in properties is occurring at higher clay concentrations. This degradation may be associated with the corresponding embrittlement.

Table 3: Flexural Properties of Polypropylene Cloisite®15A Nanocomposites

Specimen	Clay content wt. %	Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
PP-neat	0	1.5	51
PP005CL15A	0.5	2.3	69
PP01CL15A	1	2.7	72
PP02CL15A	2	2.9	93
PP03CL15A	3	3.0	95
PP05CL15A	5	2.9	83

Vickers Hardness and Notched Izod Impact Tests

The above tests were performed to understand the relationship between the hardness and impact properties for virgin and nanocomposites specimens. Table 5 shows the average hardness and impact strength of the virgin and nano-infused polypropylene specimens.

Table 4: Vickers hardness and Impact Properties of PP-CL15A Nanocomposites.

	Clay content	Vickers Hardness	Impact Strength
specimen	wt. %	HV	kJ/m ²
PP-neat	0	7.6	43
PP005CL15A	0.5	9.7	51
PP01CL15A	1	10.5	55
PP02CL15A	2	11.9	59
PP03CL15A	3	12.5	37
PP05CL15A	5	13.6	26

The hardness of the nanocomposites gradually increases with increasing clay content. PP05CL15A specimens displayed the largest hardness numbers averaging at 13.6. This corroborates the findings for the compressive properties where modulus and strength increased to a threshold value prior to degradation. Figure 7 shows increase in both the impact strength as well as the Vickers hardness number up to 2 wt. % loading. Thereafter the impact strength reduces with the corresponding increase in hardness number. Indications are that at 2 wt. % loading the material reaches a hardness number at which the impact properties degrade, mainly because of embrittlement.

Fig. 7: Impact Strength vs. Vickers hardness as a function of clay concentration.

Morphology

We earlier suggested that the enhanced properties of polypropylene infused with nanoclays may be attributed to intercalated and exfoliated structures synthesised on the nanoscale. Additionally we suggested that agglomerated micro-structures were responsible for the degradation in properties. In order to test these hypotheses, a detailed SEM study was conducted.

The fracture surfaces of tensile tested nanocomposite specimens were analysed using a Philips XL30 Environmental SEM with accelerating voltage 0.2 to 30 kV and magnification 15 to

500 000. The microscope is equipped with a conventional filament emission gun giving a beam spot size of 20 nm and image resolution of 2 nm.

Thin transverse sections, approximately 2 to 7 mm in thickness were cut from selected specimens. Figure 8 shows the fractured surface of virgin polypropylene.

Fig. 8: SEM image of fractured virgin PP tested in tension.

The surface shows a fairly homogenous polymer with minimal high stress zones. The high stress zones, depicted by the lighter lines, were formed by tensile deformation of the matrix. Examination of the fractured surfaces of the nano-infused specimens reveals a change in this morphology.

Figure 9 shows the fractured surface of polypropylene infused with 0.5 wt. % nanoclays.

Fig. 9: SEM image of fractured polypropylene infused with 0.5 wt. % nanoclays, tested in tension.

There is a distinct change in the fractured surface when compared to virgin PP sample. A network of lighter lines against the grey background and a larger ridge type structure are visible. These structures show several high stress zones which indicate the increased reinforcement of the polymer matrix. These structural phenomena may be linked to increase in the tensile modulus and strength as shown in table 2. The increases may be attributed to the homogenous and fibrillated change in morphology. Chow et al. [18] suggests that this morphology may be responsible for good interfacial adhesion resulting in the enhancement of tensile properties.

The 1 wt. % polypropylene nanocomposite structures, shown in Figure 10, has a similar morphology to the 0.5 wt. % structures.

Fig. 10: SEM image of fractured polypropylene infused with 1 wt. % nanoclays, tested in tension.

The fractured surface shows more high stress zones than virgin polypropylene and 0.5 wt. % structures. In line with this, we find that both the stiffness and strength increased to 1.9 GPa and 60 MPa respectively.

Figure 11 represents the fracture surface of polypropylene infused with 2 wt. % of nanoclays.

Fig. 11: SEM image of fractured polypropylene infused with 2 wt. % nanoclays, tested in tension.

At this clay loading, maximum enhancement in tensile properties was achieved. The structure shown is distinctly different from structures discussed thus far. It is finer and more particulate in nature. This high-density grain boundary, which shows a strengthened matrix, resulted in increased stiffness and tensile strength as discussed previously.

Further analysis of the nanocomposite structures at clay loadings greater than 2 wt. % showed a drop in tensile properties. Figure 12 represents a low magnification fractured surface of 5 wt. % specimens. Two distinct surface areas may be seen.

Fig. 12: SEM image of fractured polypropylene infused with 5 wt. % nanoclays, tested in tension.

One is particulate in nature and the other is similar to the morphology described for virgin PP. This image suggests poor infusion of nanoclays into the polymer matrix. Further inspection using a light microscope shows these areas more clearly (figure 13). The whiter agglomeration is indicative of virgin polypropylene whilst the dark brown area represents infused polypropylene.

Fig. 13: Light microscope image of fractured polypropylene infused with 5 wt. % nanoclays at 5 × magnifications.

Preliminary TEM studies indicate that agglomerated clay tactoids have formed in 5 wt. % structures. These structures impact on the interfacial interactions of the polymer molecules causing poor interfacial adhesion, a reduction in tensile properties and embrittlement in the PP nanocomposite structure [6, 8, 18]. These findings will be shown in a further study.

4. CONCLUSION

Virgin polypropylene and nanocomposite structures at the various montmorillonite nanoclay concentrations were prepared. Quasi static mechanical tests were performed to characterize the nanocomposite structures and it was found that:

- Failure strength, stiffness and fracture properties of the nano-structure were enhanced when compared to the unmodified structure.

- The mechanical properties improved with an increase in nanoclay loading up to a threshold of 2 wt. %, thereafter the material properties degraded. SEM studies at low weight loadings of the tensile fractured surfaces indicate that the morphology changes to homogenous and fibrillated and this suggests good interfacial adhesion between the nanoclays and polymer giving the added strength.
- Tensile modulus and tensile strength increased by 120 % and 160 % respectively with 2 wt. % nanoclay loading however at 3 wt. % and 5 wt. % loading property degradation in structures are evident. SEM images of 5 wt. % structures show areas of poor clay infusion and multiple agglomerations sites. This may be responsible for the degradation in properties.
- Flexural modulus and strength have increased by 97 % and 85 % respectively for specimens with 3 wt. % loading.
- Vickers hardness increased from 7.6 Hv for virgin polypropylene to 13 Hv for 5 wt. % structures with corresponding decreases in impact strength from 43 kJ/m² to 26 kJ/m². This finding suggests an embrittlement process taking place in the polymer nanocomposite matrix.

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